

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1850	Ignaz Goldziher	1862	1870	1911		Hungarian scholar of Islam	1850-1921
1850	Eduard Sievers	1870	1870	1919		German philologist of the classical and Germanic languages	1850-1932
1850	Wilhelm Bacher	1871		1913		Hungarian (Jewish) scholar, rabbi, Orientalist and linguist	1850-1913
1850	Alois Rzach	1873	1873	1923		Austrian philologist and educator	1850-1935
1850	Carl Robert	1873	1873	1922		German classical philologist and archaeologist	1850-1922
1850	Theodor Wilhelm Braune	1873		1920		German philologist and Germanist	1850-1926
1850	Charles Rockwell Lanman	1873	1873	1926		American scholar of the Sanskrit language	1850-1941
1850	Alfred Morel-Fatio	1874		1924		French leading Hispanist	1850-1924
1850	Friedrich Delitzsch	1874	1874	1920		German Assyriologist	1850-1922
1850	Wilhelm Viëtor	1875	1875	1918		German phonetician and language educator	1850-1918
1850	Fritz Schöll	1876	1876	1918		German classical philologist	1850-1919
1850	Élie Berger	1876		1925		French palaeographer and archivist	1850-1925
1850	Grigore Tocilescu	1876	1876	1909		Romanian historian, archaeologist, epigrapher and folklorist	1850-1909
1850	Samuel Butcher	1879		1910		British Anglo-Irish classical scholar and politician	1850-1910
1850	Basil Hall Chamberlain	1880		1911		British professor of Japanese at Tokyo Imperial University and one of the foremost British Japanologists	1850-1935
1850	Karl Budde	1882		1921		German authority on the Old Testament	1850-1935
1850	Hermann Carl George Brandt	1882	1896	1920		German-American scholar who published German grammars	1850-1920
1850	Jane Ellen Harrison	1882		1922 w		British classical scholar and linguist	1850-1928
1850	Heimann Hariton Tiktin	1884	1884	1925		Polish-Romanian Jewish linguist and academic, one of the founders of modern Romanian linguistics	1850-1936
1850	Anténor Firmin	1885		1910		Haitian anthropologist, journalist, and politician	1850-1911
1850	Émile Amélineau	1887	1887	1915		French Coptologist, archaeologist and Egyptologist	1850-1915
1850	Mansel Longworth Dames	1891		1922		British scholar of oriental and Portuguese languages	1850-1922
1851	George Foot Moore	1872	1872	1928		American eminent historian of religion, author, Presbyterian minister, 33rd Degree Mason of the Ancient and Accepted Scottish Rite, and accomplished teacher	1851-1931

1851	Adalbert Bezzenberger	1872	1872	1921	German philologist	1851-1922
1851	Ferdinand Kattenbusch	1873	1873	1922	German Protestant theologian, professor, dean of a theological faculty and university rector	1851-1935
1851	Émile Chatelain	1873		1933	French Latinist and palaeographer	1851-1933
1851	Otto Gruppe	1873	1873	1915	German mythographer, reading of Greek mythology through surviving texts	1851-1921
1851	Adolf von Harnack	1873	1873	1930	German Baltic Lutheran theologian and prominent church historian	1851-1930
1851	Friedrich Vogt	1873		1909	German philologist	1851-1923
1851	Herbert Hope Risley	1875	No	1911	British ethnographer and colonial administrator, a member of the Indian Civil Service who conducted extensive studies on the tribes and castes of the Bengal Presidency	1851-1911
1851	Martin Hartmann	1875	1875	1918	German Orientalist, who specialized in Islamic studies.	1851-1918
1851	Martijn Theodoor Houtsma	1875	1875	1938	Dutch orientalist and professor at the University of Utrecht	1851-1943
1851	Johan August Lundell	1876	1876	1918	Swedish linguist, professor of Slavic languages	1851-1940
1851	Heinrich Zimmer	1876	1876	1910	German Celtologist and Indologist	1851-1910
1851	Friedrich Leo	1878		1914	German classical philologist	1851-1914
1851	Eberhard Nestle	1879		1912	German biblical scholar, textual critic, orientalist, editor of the <i>Novum Testamentum Graece</i>	1851-1913
1851	Francis Hindes Groome	1881		1902	British writer and foremost commentator of his time on the Romani people, their language, life, history, customs, beliefs, and lore	1851-1902
1851	George Abraham Grierson	1883	No	1925	Irish administrator and linguist in British India	1851-1941
1851	Jane Dieulafoy	1887		1915	w French archaeologist, explorer, novelist and journalist	1851-1916
1851	Nikolay Zograf	1887		1919	Russian zoologist and anthropologist	1851-1919
1851	Carl Sofus Lumholtz	1889	No	1922	Norwegian explorer and ethnographer, best known for his meticulous field research and ethnographic publications on indigenous cultures of Australia and Mexico	1851-1922
1852	Kazimierz Morawski	1874	1874	1925	Polish classical philologist, historian, translator, professor and rector of Jagiellonian University, president of Polish Academy of Learning	1852-1925

1852	Karl Friedrich Geldner	1875	1875	1921	German linguist best known for his analysis and synthesis of Avestan and Vedic Sanskrit texts	1852-1929
1852	René Verneau	1875		1932	French palaeoanthropologist	1852-1938
1852	Georg Loeschcke	1876		1915	German archaeologist	1852-1915
1852	Georg Wenker	1876	1876	1911	German linguist who began documenting German dialect geography during the late nineteenth century	1852-1911
1852	Maximilian Berlitz	1877		1921	German-American linguist and the founder of the Berlitz Language Schools	1852-1921
1852	Adolf Schlatter	1879	1879	1922	German world-leading Protestant theologian and professor specialising in the New Testament and systematics	1852-1938
1852	Olof August Danielsson	1879	1879	1917	Swedish linguist and classical philologist	1852-1933
1852	Hermann Freiherr von Soden	1880		1914	German Biblical scholar, minister, professor of divinity, and textual theorist	1852-1914
1852	James Bright	1882	1882	1925	American Professor of English Philology (early Germanic languages and Old and Middle English)	1852-1926
1852	Arthur Leist	1885		1922	German writer, journalist and translator of Georgian and Armenian literature	1852-1927
1852	Joseph Deniker	1886	1886	1918	Russian-French naturalist and anthropologist, known primarily for his attempts to develop highly detailed maps of race in Europe	1852-1918
1852	John Gwenogvryn Evans	1887	1901	1924	British Welsh palaeographic expert and literary translator	1852-1930
1852	Johannes François Snelleman	1887	No	1915	Dutch zoologist, orientalist, ethnographer and museum director	1852-1938
1852	Frederick W. Baller	1891		1919	British Protestant Christian missionary to China, Chinese linguist, translator, educator and sinologist	1852-1922
1853	Albert Stanburrough Cook	1872		1927	American philologist, literary critic, and scholar of Old English	1853-1927
1853	Just Knud Qvigstad	1874	1874	1931	Norwegian philologist, linguist, ethnographer, historian and cultural historian	1853-1957
1853	Erich Schmidt	1875		1913	German historian of literature	1853-1913
1853	Jacob Wackernagel	1875	1875	1936	Swiss linguist, Indo-Europeanist and scholar of Sanskrit	1853-1938
1853	Rudolf Kittel	1876	1876	1919	German Old Testament scholar	1853-1929

1853	Hara Prasad Shastri	1876		1924	Indian academic, Sanskrit scholar, archivist and historian of Bengali literature	1853-1931
1853	Ferdinand Karsch	1877	1877	1921	German arachnologist, entomologist and anthropologist	1853-1936
1853	Bernhard Seuffert	1877	1877	1924	German-Austrian philologist, specializing in German studies	1853-1938
1853	Florentino Ameghino	1878	No	1911	Argentinean naturalist, paleontologist, anthropologist and zoologist, whose fossil discoveries on the Argentine Pampas, especially on Patagonia, rank with those made in the western United States during the late 19th century	1853-1911
1853	Henri Pognon	1878		1914	French archaeologist, epigrapher, specialist in Assyriology	1853-1921
1853	Frank Bigelow Tarbell	1879	1879	1918	American professor of Classic Studies	1853-1920
1853	Bernard Haussoullier	1879		1926	French Hellenist, epigrapher and archaeologist	1853-1926
1853	Gottfried Baist	1880	1880	1918	German Hispanist and Romance studies scholar	1853-1920
1853	Franz Wickhoff	1880	1880	1909	Austrian art historian, and is considered a member of the Vienna School of Art History	1853-1909
1853	Kārlis Mīlenbahs	1880	1880	1916	Latvian he first native speaker of Latvian to devote his career to linguistics	1853-1916
1853	Alf Torp	1881		1916	Norwegian philologist and author	1853-1916
1853	William Henry Carpenter	1881		1920	American philologist	1853-1936
1853	Theodor Vetter	1881	1881	1913	Swiss Anglist	1853-1922
1853	Henri Goelzer	1883	1883	1929	French classical philologist	1853-1929
1853	Flinders Petrie	1885	1897	1933	British English Egyptologist and a pioneer of systematic methodology in archaeology and preservation of artefacts	1853-1942
1853	John Percival Postgate	1885		1920	British English classicist, professor of Latin	1853-1926
1853	Andrew Fleming West	1888	No	1928	American classicist, and first dean of the Graduate School at Princeton University	1853-1943
1853	Augustus Hamilton	1893		1913	New Zealand ethnologist, biologist and museum director	1853-1913
1854	James George Frazer	1874	1874	1921	British Scottish social anthropologist and folklorist influential in the early stages of the modern studies of mythology and comparative religion	1854-1941

1854	Clément Huart	1875	1875	1926	French orientalist, publisher and translators of Persian, Turkish and Arabic writings	1854-1926
1854	Anton Bezenšek	1875		1915	Slovenian linguist, journalist, shorthand expert, and lecturer	1854-1915
1854	Rajko Perušek	1876		1910	Slovenian writer, translator, linguist and bibliographer	1854-1917
1854	Heinrich Morf	1877	1877	1921	Swiss linguist and literary historian	1854-1921
1854	Adolf Noreen	1877	1877	1925	Swedish linguist	1854-1925
1854	Fritz Hommel	1877	1877	1925	German Orientalist	1854-1936
1854	Hartwig Hirschfeld	1878	1878	1929	British Prussian-born Orientalist, bibliographer, and educator	1854-1934
1854	E. J. Dillon	1878		1933	Irish author, journalist and linguist	1854-1933
1854	Felix von Luschan	1878	1878	1922	Austrian doctor, anthropologist, explorer, archaeologist and ethnographer	1854-1924
1854	J. G. Garson	1878	1878	1916	British Scottish anthropologist	1854-1932
1854	Georges Vacher de Lapouge	1879	1879	1922	French anthropologist and a theoretician of eugenics and racialism	1854-1936
1854	Jules Gilliéron	1880		1926	Swiss-French linguist and dialectologist	1854-1926
1854	Adolf Erman	1880		1934	German renowned German Egyptologist and lexicographer	1854-1937
1854	Ioannis Psycharis	1881		1928	Ukrainian-French philologist of Greek origin, author and promoter of Demotic Greek	1854-1929
1854	Thomas Stangl	1882	1882	1919	German classical scholar and text critic	1854-1921
1854	Calvin Thomas	1882		1919	American scholar, professor of Germanic languages and literature	1854-1919
1854	Benjamin Ide Wheeler	1885	1885	1919	American professor of Greek and comparative philology	1854-1927
1854	Charles W. Wason	1888		1918	American engineer, Orientalist, philanthropist and bibliophile	1854-1918